

1 **Function of the E6 protein of type 16 and type 84 in HaCaT cells.**

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7 We used next generation sequencing to describe in an unbiased fashion molecular functions of the E6
8 protein of high-risk HPV16 versus that of HPV84, a lower risk type. We demonstrate here selective
9 oncogene activation by type 16 E6 protein, including *Gli2* and *Fli1*. HPV16 and HPV84 E6 had shared
10 (*Clec7a*) and unique (*Prss21* by HPV16 E6) immune receptor targets. High-risk HPV16 E6 displayed
11 special morphogen control including silencing of *Bmp7* and repression of *Wnt5a*.

12 Citations

13 1. Crook, T., Vousden, K.H. and Tidy, J.A., 1991. Degradation of p53 can be targeted by HPV E6
14 sequences distinct from those required for p53 binding and trans-activation. *Cell*, 67(3), pp.547-556.

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